

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF NURSES' CONFLICT BEHAVIOR AND ITS ROLE IN TEAM PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The effectiveness of a healthcare organization largely depends on the quality of interaction with qualified nursing staff. Nurses represent the largest professional category in the healthcare system and play a vital role in ensuring high-quality medical care. One of the key internal factors affecting the success of their performance is job satisfaction. A low level of satisfaction makes it impossible to achieve sustainable development and strong organizational outcomes.

This study aims to identify behavioral strategies used by nurses in conflict situations and examine their association with job satisfaction. Conflicts are viewed as major stressors that can reduce motivation, weaken team cohesion, and undermine the emotional well-being of personnel. A nurse's behavioral response to conflict significantly influences the collective climate and the effectiveness of team activities.

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional observational study was conducted in 2023 at a state clinical hospital in Almaty. A total of 281 nurses participated in the survey. The minimum required sample size was 248 respondents, based on a general population of 696. Data were collected through an online questionnaire (Google Forms). Behavioral strategies were analyzed using Pearson's chi-square test, Fisher's exact test, relative risk (RR), and binary logistic regression. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

The most common behavioral strategies were accommodation — 45.91%, competition — 29.54% ($p < 0.001$), compromise and avoidance — 49.47%, and collaboration — 51.96%. Statistically significant correlations were found between job satisfaction and the strategies of accommodation ($RR=1.589$; $p=0.002$), compromise ($RR=1.571$; $p=0.003$), and avoidance ($RR=1.404$; $p=0.002$). The findings confirm that unresolved conflicts negatively affect employee morale and productivity, and may lead to serious disruptions in teamwork.

The results highlight the importance of systematically developing nurses' communication skills, resilience, and constructive conflict resolution abilities.

Keywords: conflict, job satisfaction, nurse, team.

Introduction

A significant share of responsibility for the quality of medical care lies with the nursing staff [1]. Today, the role of a nurse is increasingly recognized as that of an equal partner to physicians, capable of independently assessing patient conditions and making clinical decisions [2]. The effectiveness of teamwork in medical institutions is strongly dependent on the collaboration between doctors and nurses, whose relationships have historically taken on a special dynamic [3].

Successful communication is built upon mutual respect, active listening, and the ability to perceive the emotional state of others [4, 5]. As the largest group in the healthcare workforce, nurses play a vital role in addressing system-wide challenges. Therefore, identifying internal factors to enhance their performance remains relevant [6]. One such factor is job satisfaction. Additionally, the introduction of new management models in healthcare must consider the socio-economic context of each country. In Kazakhstan, this area remains underexplored [7]. As human capital has become

central to organizational effectiveness, job satisfaction is recognized as a key indicator—its absence undermines productivity [8]. This study seeks to identify the primary causes of dissatisfaction among nurses, such as conflict, lack of motivation, and excessive workloads. The psychosocial climate in the workplace influences care quality, patient safety, and staff retention [9]. International nursing practices show a shift from traditional hospital care to roles emphasizing health maintenance and disease prevention [10]. Concerns over interpersonal conflict are growing in clinical settings, driven by communication gaps and relational issues in closed environments like hospitals [11]. Inadequate communication can lead to misunderstandings, reduced trust, dissatisfaction, and even medical errors [12]. While most research focuses on office environments, a few studies have highlighted how workplace design in healthcare impacts team dynamics and outcomes [13]. Workplace climate is known to affect nursing care quality. Positive environments reduce burnout and enhance job satisfaction and patient outcomes [14, 15]. Supportive teamwork and cooperative culture help reduce turnover intentions [16, 17, 18], while personal competencies also contribute to better outcomes [19]. Conflict is a natural phenomenon in any social context and often stems from poor communication, arrogance, stress, and unprofessional behavior [20, 21]. Such conflicts are becoming more frequent in healthcare settings, including among nurses [22]. Given the ambiguity of roles and workload, nurses are particularly vulnerable to burnout. Positive attitudes and favorable working conditions are crucial [23]. Unresolved conflict undermines team support and care quality. Effective conflict management strengthens team safety, nursing performance, and overall patient care [24, 25]. While most existing literature focuses on communication between nurses and physicians [26], there is a notable gap in Kazakhstan regarding nursing conflict management. This underscores the importance of studying nurses' work conditions, communication skills, and readiness for team collaboration.

The aim of this study is to explore the relationship between the team's psychosocial climate, the level of conflict, and job satisfaction among nurses. The results will inform strategies for developing communication skills, conflict resolution, and a healthier workplace environment to improve nursing effectiveness.

Materials and Methods

This study was designed as a cross-sectional observational analysis using analytical statistical methods. Data collection was carried out in 2023 through an

online questionnaire (Google Forms) at a state clinical hospital in Almaty. A total of 281 nurses participated in the survey. The minimum required sample size was calculated to be 248 respondents, based on a total population of 696 individuals and a 95% confidence level, making the obtained sample statistically representative. The questionnaire used in the study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Al-Farabi Kazakh National University (decision dated June 22, 2023, No. IRB-A637) and registered with the national intellectual property registry (Certificate of Copyright Registration No. 36334 dated May 29, 2023). An informed consent form accompanied the questionnaire, detailing all ethical aspects of the research. The collected data were processed using IBM SPSS Statistics software. To assess nurses' behavioral strategies in conflict situations, Pearson's chi-square test and/or Fisher's exact test were applied, along with the calculation of relative risk (RR) and binary logistic regression. Additionally, one-sample binomial and one-sample chi-square tests were used. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 281 nurses participated in the survey. Among them, 64 nurses (22.78%) were under the age of 30, 143 nurses (50.89%) were between the ages of 30 and 50, and 74 nurses (26.33%) were over the age of 50. Regarding professional experience, 15 respondents (5.34%) had less than one year of experience, 115 nurses (40.93%) had between 1 and 10 years, 122 nurses (43.42%) had between 10 and 30 years, and 29 nurses (10.32%) had over 30 years of experience. Most of the respondents—234 nurses (83.27%)—were engaged in direct clinical practice, 10 nurses (3.56%) held administrative positions, and 37 nurses (13.17%) performed other professional functions.

The study analyzed the behavioral strategies of nurses in conflict situations. The results showed that 45.91% (129 respondents) tended to be accommodating (adaptation), 29.54% adopted a dominant approach (compulsion, $p \leq 0.001$), 49.47% preferred to avoid or seek compromise ($p = 0.905$), and 51.96% demonstrated a willingness to collaborate ($p = 0.551$).

Table 1 presents the distribution of behavioral strategies based on the level of job satisfaction. Statistically significant predictors of job satisfaction included: "accommodation" (RR=1.589, $p = 0.002$), "compromise" (RR=1.571, $p = 0.003$), and "avoidance" (RR=1.404, $p = 0.002$).

Table 1

Strategies of behavior of nurses in conflict situations, taking into account their level of job satisfaction.

Behavioral Strategies in Response to Conflict Situations		Satisfaction of Nurses with Their Job Performance		p-value
		Complete Satisfaction	Satisfied, and/or Partially Satisfied	
Adaptation or Concession to the Opponent ('You Win - I Lose')	probably not", than "yes"	73	79	p=0,002
	more like "yes" than "no"	39	90	
Opponent Suppression ('I won - You lost')	probably not", than "yes"	86	112	p=0,059
	more like "yes" than "no"	26	57	
Compromise ('I gained a slight advantage - You gained a slight advantage')	probably not", than "yes"	69	73	p=0,003
	more like "yes" than "no"	43	96	
Avoidance of Conflict ('You lost - I lost')	probably not", than "yes"	66	76	p=0,022
	more like "yes" than "no"	46	93	
Cooperation ('I have gained - You have gained')	probably not", than "yes"	61	74	p=0,079
	more like "yes" than "no"	51	95	

Table 2

Characteristics of predictors that make a statistically significant contribution to the predictive ability of the regression model.

Variables in the Equation		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 1	Freedom of Expression in a Collective Setting	3,050	1,026	8,831	1	0,003	21,106
	Constant	-3,296	1,018	10,475	1	0,001	0,037
Step 2	Free Expression of Opinion in a Collective Setting	2,677	1,037	6,669	1	0,010	14,542
	Moral and Psychological Climate in the Collective	2,119	0,754	7,895	1	0,005	8,322
	Constant	-4,923	1,235	15,887	1	0,000	0,007
Step 3	Free Expression of Opinion in a Collective Setting	2,775	1,041	7,103	1	0,008	16,040
	Moral and Psychological Climate in the Collective	2,045	0,759	7,252	1	0,007	7,727
	Compromise ('I gain a little - You gain a little')	0,776 -	0,262	8,766	1	0,003	2,173
	Constant	-6,128	1,316	21,694	1	0,000	0,002

Table 2 summarizes the predictors that contributed significantly to the regression model. The analysis was performed using binary logistic regression. The dependent variable was job satisfaction: 0 = "dissatisfied/partially satisfied" and 1 = "fully satisfied". The model was built using the Wald stepwise method. Three key predictors were identified in the third step: "freedom to express opinions within the team", "psychological climate in the team", and "compromise". The overall model classification accuracy was 65.8%.

Discussion

Nurses play a crucial role in fostering effective teamwork, which significantly influences interpersonal relationships within the healthcare team and ultimately affects health outcomes [27]. Ensuring quality and safe patient care is not possible without sufficient numbers of qualified nursing staff. However, the global nursing shortage remains a critical issue, exacerbated by the increasing demand for healthcare services due to population aging [28].

The core philosophy of nursing emphasizes respect for human life and the dignity of every individual. Effective communication requires not only listening but also showing empathy, recognizing each person's uniqueness and right to participate in decision-making [29]. Establishing trust-based, responsible relationships between nurses and patients is fundamental to nursing practice [30].

Interpersonal conflicts are inevitable, even in strong professional relationships. Nevertheless, the constructive management of disagreements can build trust and deepen mutual understanding [31, 32]. This requires knowledge of conflict behavior strategies and the ability to apply them appropriately depending on the context [33, 34].

Teamwork in healthcare settings demands a high level of coordination and readiness to compromise. Despite its benefits, teamwork can be disrupted by destructive conflicts and poor communication [35–37]. Barriers such as communication avoidance, inadequate listening skills, or inappropriate interaction styles negatively affect the team climate [38, 39].

Conflicts arising from personal or organizational causes may impair team functionality and cause tension. Differences in values, goals, or cultural norms frequently lead to misunderstandings [40, 41]. These conflicts often result in diminished morale, decreased productivity, and large-scale confrontations [42].

As the largest professional group in healthcare, nurses frequently experience conflict and heavy workloads but may lack the necessary skills to manage these challenges. Consequently, unresolved conflicts can reduce job satisfaction and contribute to higher staff turnover [43, 44].

Chronic conflict is associated with absenteeism, decreased collaboration, reduced care quality, and an increased likelihood of medical errors [45]. Therefore, conflict management must be prioritized in healthcare institutions.

This study confirmed statistically significant correlations between job satisfaction and conflict behavior strategies such as accommodation, compromise, and avoidance ($p < 0.05$). The accommodation strategy

("You win – I lose") was associated with job dissatisfaction among 32% of nurses ($p=0.002$). This may reflect a tendency to preserve workplace harmony at the expense of personal needs, which can lead to internal stress and emotional burnout.

Similarly, 34.1% of respondents who chose the compromise strategy ("We both win a little") also reported dissatisfaction ($p=0.003$). Although compromise is often seen as a fair resolution, it can feel like a temporary measure, potentially leaving individuals with an unexpressed personal stance.

The avoidance strategy ("You lose – I lose") was linked to dissatisfaction among 33% of participants ($p=0.022$). This approach is often used due to lack of confidence, poor coping skills, or passive attitudes. Unfortunately, avoidance can hinder open dialogue and escalate team tension, obstructing constructive collaboration.

These behavioral patterns are ineffective in the long term and may undermine the productivity and efficacy of nursing teams. Inefficient conflict resolution erodes trust, disrupts communication, and compromises the quality of healthcare services.

In this context, leadership—particularly dialogic and transformational styles—becomes essential for conflict prevention and resolution. Open communication, mutual respect, and negotiation skills reinforce team cohesion and improve care quality [46].

Studies by Delak B and Širok K (2021) showed that the most commonly used conflict resolution styles among nurses were avoidance and compromise. Similar findings were reported by Baçoğul C and Aseery M, indicating that these two strategies dominate in nursing practice [47–49].

Therefore, the development of conflict management competencies should be an integral part of nurse education and professional development. Such training fosters team trust, reduces burnout, and enhances the quality of healthcare [50].

Our findings affirm that sustainable teamwork and effective professional interactions cannot be achieved without systematic training for nurse leaders and practitioners in conflict resolution strategies. Core competencies such as communication, leadership, and teamwork must be cultivated throughout all stages of professional growth [51–53].

Conclusions and Practical Recommendations

The findings of our study revealed that in conflict situations, the most commonly adopted behavioral strategies among hospital nurses were **accommodation** and **compromise**, followed by **avoidance**. Unlike the results of some previously published studies [49], the strategy of **collaboration** did not demonstrate a statistically significant association with job satisfaction. This is a noteworthy observation, as collaboration is generally regarded as the most effective approach for maintaining a positive and constructive work environment in healthcare settings. Our data partially align with the results reported by Baçoğul C et al. and Delak B and Širok.

Based on the analysis, we propose the following measures to prevent and mitigate conflict within nursing teams:

1. Implementation of communication skills training: Regular workshops and training sessions focused on effective communication and conflict management should be introduced. These interventions will enable nurses to adopt constructive behavioral strategies and promote cohesion, mutual understanding, and psychological well-being within the team.

2. Development of educational programs on communication styles: Specialized programs aimed at enhancing personal competencies and communication skills should be integrated into professional development. These initiatives are expected to improve both interpersonal and professional relationships and contribute to a healthier workplace climate.

3. Provision of psychological support and self-regulation techniques: For nurses exhibiting moderate to high levels of conflict proneness, it is advisable to offer psychological self-regulation training. This may include the establishment of relaxation or stress-relief rooms, where staff can learn coping strategies and stress management techniques to enhance their resilience and reduce workplace tension.

In summary, our findings emphasize that conflicts among nursing staff remain a significant concern and require targeted interventions. Effective conflict resolution largely depends on the ability of healthcare managers and unit leaders to identify root causes and promote dialogue and compromise. Ultimately, successful conflict management is facilitated by a workplace culture grounded in trust, mutual respect, and a shared commitment to team unity and collaboration.

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